

VISUALIZATION OF STRAIN CONCENTRATIONS IN COMPOSITES USING ADVANCED IMAGE PROCESSING TECHNIQUES

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ABSTRACT

Full-field strain distributions of two titanium (Ti) alloys in tensile tests were non-destructively investigated in a small region using digital image correlation (DIC) and in a large area using a developed moiré technique in complementary ways. The crack occurrence locations were successfully predicted from microscale strain concentrations. Moreover, slip lines in oblique angles were found to emerge on Ti alloys under greater tensile loads.

1 INTRODUCTION

Owing to high tensile strength and toughness even at high temperatures, Ti alloys hold great promise for applications in automobiles, aircraft, spacecraft, etc. However, local damage always arises due to the complicated deformation caused by their multi-phase microstructures. As one of the most common and typical Ti alloys used in engines, Titanium 6-Aluminium 4-Vanadium (Ti-6Al-4V) alloy has an hcp/bcc laminated microstructure, where strain localization occurs easily along the microstructure interface or boundary [1]. To investigate its instability behaviours and failure mechanisms, it is indispensable to detect the strain concentration locations before microscale crack occurrence non-destructively.

As non-contact, high-accuracy and full-field optical methods, the DIC method and the moiré technique are chosen as the research approaches for strain imaging in this study. The DIC method [2, 3] has been extensively used in deformation measurement due to simpleness and several commercial software products. The moiré technique is also popular in the precision measurement fields owing to advantages of high noise resistance and deformation visualization. In recent years, moiré interferometry, the microscope scanning moiré method [4], the digital moiré method [5] and the sampling moiré method [6, 7] have been developed and applied for deformation measurement from nanoscale to the meter scale.

In this work, the microscale deformation distributions of two Ti-6Al-4V specimens were measured by advanced digital image correlation (DIC) and a developed sampling moiré [8] technique complementarily to visualize the strain concentrations in tensile tests.

2 METHODS

The deformation measurement principles of the DIC method and the developed 2D moiré phase analysis method will be introduced in this section.

2.1 Digital image correlation method

The DIC method uses a speckle as its deformation carrier. A cross-correlation function is adopted to find the maximum of the correlation array between subsets of pixel intensity arrays on the un-

deformed and deformed images, which gives the translational shift, i.e., displacement [3]. The strains can be calculated from the partial differentials of displacements in different directions.

2.2 2D moiré phase analysis method

To determine the strain distributions accurately from a single-shot grid image on a specimen, the 2D moiré phase analysis method was developed by integrating the sampling moiré method and a 2D phase analysis [8]. The measurement principle will be introduced in detail.

A 2D grid includes two gratings, i.e., grating X and grating Y , shown in Fig. 1. The intensity of the 2D grid before deformation can be represented by

$$I = A_X \cos\left[2\pi\left(\frac{x}{p_{Xx}} + \frac{y}{p_{Yy}}\right)\right] + A_Y \cos\left[2\pi\left(\frac{x}{p_{Yx}} + \frac{y}{p_{Yy}}\right)\right] + B \quad (1)$$

where A_X and A_Y stand for the modulated amplitudes of grating X and grating Y , respectively, p_{Xx} and p_{Xy} are the pitches of grating X in the x and y directions, respectively, p_{Yx} and p_{Yy} denote the pitches of grating Y in the x and y directions, respectively, and B includes the background and higher-order intensities.

Figure 1: (a) Diagram of a 2D grid on a specimen, and (b) geometric relationship of gratings before and after deformation.

After using a low pass or Fourier transform filter to the 2D grid image, grating X and grating Y can be extracted, and their intensities can be respectively expressed as

$$I_X = A_X \cos\left[2\pi\left(\frac{x}{p_{Xx}} + \frac{y}{p_{Xy}}\right)\right] + B_X = A_X \cos \varphi_X + B_X \quad (2)$$

$$I_Y = A_Y \cos\left[2\pi\left(\frac{x}{p_{Yx}} + \frac{y}{p_{Yy}}\right)\right] + B_Y = A_Y \cos \varphi_Y + B_Y \quad (3)$$

where B_X and B_Y mean the background and higher-order intensities of grating X and grating Y , respectively. and φ_X and φ_Y signify the phases of grating X and grating Y , respectively.

Similarly, the intensities of the 2D grid, grating X' and grating Y' after deformation can also be represented by Eqs. (1)-(3) through adding single quotes to all variables, such as changing I to I' .

Each grating can be used to generate spatial phase-shifting sampling moiré fringes by down-sampling and intensity interpolation, as seen in Fig. 2(a). Taking grating X before deformation as an example, the intensities of T_x -step phase shifting sampling moiré fringes can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_{X,mx}(k_x) &= A_X \cos\left[2\pi\left(\frac{x}{p_{Xx}} + \frac{y}{p_{Xy}} - \frac{x}{T_x} + \frac{k_x}{T_x}\right)\right] + B_X \\
 &= A_X \cos\left[\varphi_{X,mx} + 2\pi\frac{k_x}{T_x}\right] + B_X \quad (k_x = 0, 1, \dots, T_x - 1)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{4}$$

where $\varphi_{X,mx}$ represents the phase of moiré fringes when $k_x=0$ generated from grating X in the x direction, which is obtainable from the phase-shifting technique using a discrete Fourier transform algorithm using the following equation

$$\varphi_{X,mx} = -\arctan \frac{\sum_{k_x=0}^{T_x-1} I_{X,mx}(k_x) \sin(2\pi k_x / T_x)}{\sum_{k_x=0}^{T_x-1} I_{X,mx}(k_x) \cos(2\pi k_x / T_x)}
 \tag{5}$$

Similarly, the phase $\varphi_{Y,my}$ of moiré fringes generated from grating Y in the y direction, $\varphi'_{X,mx}$ of moiré fringes generated from grating X' after deformation in the x direction, and $\varphi'_{Y,my}$ of moiré fringes generated from grating Y' after deformation in the y direction are also acquirable using equations similar to Eqs. (4) and (5). Therefore, the phase differences of moiré fringes in the x and y directions can be calculated from

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Delta\varphi_{X,mx} &= \varphi'_{X,mx} - \varphi_{X,mx} \\
 \Delta\varphi_{Y,my} &= \varphi'_{Y,my} - \varphi_{Y,my}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{6}$$

Since the phase differences of moiré fringes are the same to the phase differences of gratings, the displacement of the specimen can be determined by [8]

$$\begin{pmatrix} u_x \\ u_y \end{pmatrix} = -\frac{1}{2\pi} \begin{pmatrix} 1/p_{Xx} & 1/p_{Xy} \\ 1/p_{Yx} & 1/p_{Yy} \end{pmatrix}^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} \Delta\varphi_{X,mx} \\ \Delta\varphi_{Y,my} \end{pmatrix} = -\frac{M}{2\pi} \begin{pmatrix} \Delta\varphi_{X,mx} \\ \Delta\varphi_{Y,my} \end{pmatrix}
 \tag{7}$$

where M indicates the matrix composed of four pitches of gratings X and Y in the x and y directions.

Figure 2: Measurement principle and process of the 2D moiré phase analysis method, (a) phase measurement principle by generating phase-shifting sampling moiré fringes, and (b) measurement process of strain distributions from phase differences in the x and y directions.

From the partial differentials of displacements, the strain components are measurable

$$\begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx} & \varepsilon_{xy} \\ \varepsilon_{yx} & \varepsilon_{yy} \end{pmatrix} = -\frac{M}{2\pi} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial \Delta \varphi_{X,mx}}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial \Delta \varphi_{X,mx}}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial \Delta \varphi_{Y,my}}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial \Delta \varphi_{Y,my}}{\partial y} \end{pmatrix}, \quad \gamma_{xy} = \varepsilon_{xy} + \varepsilon_{yx} \quad (8)$$

The measurement process of strain distributions from phase differences is illustrated in Fig. 2(b). The phase differences in the x and y directions are conjointly analyzed for deformation measurement. This method has high strain measurement accuracy, and the relative error of the measured shear strain relative to the theoretical value is greatly decreased from 50% to 0.8% compared with the traditional sampling moiré method.

3 EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

The strain distributions of two Ti alloy samples in tensile tests were measured by the DIC and 2D moiré phase analysis methods, respectively, for predicting crack occurrence locations.

3.1 Specimen preparation and experimental setup

The specimen material was Ti-6.29Al-4.35V-0.155O-0.225Fe (Ti-6Al-4V for short) alloy. The geometric profiles of the two specimens are the same, as presented in Fig. 3(a). The thickness and the minimum width were 1 mm and 1.8 mm, respectively. The difference was that there was a prefabricated notch on specimen #1 to narrow the area of the stress concentration, while no prefabricated defect existed on specimen #2, shown in Fig. 3(b).

On specimen #1, the notch with width of 5 μm and length of 100 μm was produced by focused ion beam milling. A 500-nm-pitch grid pattern was fabricated by electron beam lithography in a small area of $500 \times 500 \mu\text{m}^2$ around one end of the notch, see Fig. 3(c). The tensile test was carried out in a FEI QUANTA 200F field emission scanning electron microscope (SEM), and a series of grid images were recorded when the magnification was 10000 \times during the test.

For specimen #2 without any prefabricated defect, because it is not known where the strain concentration happens easier before measurement, a 3- μm -pitch grid was fabricated in a large area of $1.8 \times 15 \text{ mm}^2$ by UV nanoimprint lithography, represented in Fig. 3(c). The wavelength of UV was 375 nm and the illumination time was 30s. The tensile test was performed under a Lasertec HYBRID laser scanning microscope (LSM), and a sequence of grid images were collected under an objective lens with magnification of 10 \times .

Figure 3: (a) Specimen geometry of the Ti-6Al-4V alloy, (b) surface images in the central area of specimens #1 and #2, where the region of interest on #2 is labeled by a blue square, and (c) images of 500-nm-pitch grid on #1 and 3- μm -pitch grid on #2.

3.2 Strain distributions of Ti alloys and discussion

The deformation distributions of specimen #1 in a small region near the notch were measured by the DIC method, and those of specimen #2 in a large area were measured by the developed 2D moiré phase analysis method.

The deformation distributions in $23 \times 18 \mu\text{m}^2$ near the notch were analysed by DIC [1]. Figs. 4(a)-4(d) show an example of the grid image and the distributions of the x -direction strain, the y -direction strain and the shear strain on specimen #1 under 511 MPa. Strain concentrations are observable near the notch from the strain distributions. The x -direction strain is maximum and the y -direction strain is minimum along the oblique line from the middle of the end of the notch.

Full-field deformation distributions in a large area were measured by the developed moiré method. Strain concentrations were found out in a square region near the specimen edge labelled in Fig. 3(b). The grid image in the square region of $219 \times 204 \mu\text{m}^2$ and the x -direction, y -direction and shear strain distributions were illustrated in Figs. 4(e)-4(f) taking the case when the tensile stress was 604 MPa as an example. The absolute values of the x -direction strain and the shear strain are maximum at a prior β grain boundary perpendicular to the tensile direction. The y -direction strain is minimum at lower parts of the grain boundary, but the absolute value is smaller.

Figure 4: (a)-(d) Grid and strain distributions in $23 \times 18 \mu\text{m}^2$ measured by DIC on specimen #1 with a notch, and (e)-(h) grid and strain distributions in $219 \times 204 \mu\text{m}^2$ obtained by Moiré on specimen #2 before crack occurrence.

Figure 5: Verification of crack occurrence locations after greater tensile stresses and unloading, (a) SEM image on specimen #1, and (b) LSM image on specimen #2.

Our experiments have verified that a crack occurs along the oblique line of strain concentration on specimen #1, and an incipient crack emerges along the strain concentration line at the grain boundary on specimen #2 after greater tensile stress and unloading, as seen in Fig. 5. It indicates that strain concentrations visualized using image processing enables accurate prediction of microscale crack occurrence.

Furthermore, slip lines with different oblique angles were observed in different grains on specimen #2 when the tensile stress reached 682 MPa. These slip lines were visible from the distribution of a component of shear strain ε_{yx} in Eq. (8). From Fig. 5(b) after unloading, the specimen has experienced a plastic shear deformation. It is helpful for understanding an underlying damage mechanism of Ti alloys around grain boundaries.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Summarily, microscale strain concentrations of Ti alloys were visualized in a small region around a notch root and in a large area from the strain mapping using DIC and Moiré methods complementarily. The crack occurrence locations were successfully predicted and slip lines in oblique angles were found to arise in tensile tests.

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